

ESTIMATION OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE CARDIOVASCULAR MANIFESTATIONS IN OSTEOARTHRITIS

Ismoilov N. U., Mamajonov Sh. T., Murodov O. A., Ergashev A. Z.,

Qobilov N. R., Mirzaakhmedov F. M., Xayitov A. A.

Tashkent Medical Academy, Uzbekistan

Annotation: Osteoarthritis (OA), atherosclerosis and coronary heart disease (CHD) share common pathophysiological mechanisms associated with systemic and chronic inflammation. At the same time, traditional risk factors, such as hypertension, elderly age, smoking, hypercholesterolemia, obesity and sex, cannot fully explain the mechanism for the accelerated development of atherosclerosis in patients with OA. Specific risk factors, such as its duration, glucocorticoid use, anti-doublestranded (native) DNA autoantibodies and antiphospholipid antibodies, create conditions for the accelerated development of atherosclerosis in this group of patients. Purpose of the study. To evaluate the frequency of traditional cardiovascular risk factors, clinical and subclinical manifestations of atherosclerosis in patients with OA. Material and methods. We examined 70 patients with a reliable diagnosis of OA (66 women and 4 men), cf. age 46 ± 10.8 years. Control group - 50 "conditionally" healthy volunteers without systemic rheumatic diseases, matched by sex and age. Results. The prevalence of traditional cardiovascular risk factors and TFR% were comparable in patients with OA and in the control group. The frequency of menopause was higher in patients with OA ($p=0.005$). IHD was diagnosed more often in patients with OA (13% vs. 2%, $p<0.05$). The mean triglyceride level in OA patients was significantly higher than in the control group ($p<0.001$). There was a tendency to increase TIM max. and the frequency of thickening of the IMT complex in patients with OA compared with the control group. Conclusion. Among OA patients, there was a higher prevalence of clinical and subclinical manifestations of atherosclerosis compared with the control group, with no significant differences in the incidence of major cardiovascular risk factors.

Key words: Osteoarthritis, atherosclerosis, cardiovascular risk factors.

Introduction. Osteoarthritis (OA) is a pathological lesion of the joints, characterized by structural changes in the articular cartilage and subchondral bone, as well as clearly or imperceptibly moderate synovitis. Osteoarthritis is an urgent medical and social problem for most countries of the world due to its high prevalence, which reaches about 25% of the population. This disease is most common among women and is one of the causes of reduced work capacity and increased disability [1–3]. The prevalence of the disease varies from 1.4 to 11 cases per 100,000 population [4]. Along with a diverse clinical picture during the course of the disease, a characteristic “bimodality” can be distinguished. Thus, in the first three years after diagnosis, the predominant cause that determines the severity of the disease and the mortality of patients is kidney damage and infectious complications against the background of high disease activity. However, the second peak in mortality, 4–20 years after diagnosis, is predominantly caused by cardiovascular disease (CVD) [5, 6]. It should be noted that, while all-cause mortality in OA has significantly decreased over the past decades due to the increase in the effectiveness of therapy, mortality from cardiovascular diseases

remains at a high level and they remain the leading cause of death in patients [7, 8]. At the same time, it should be noted the high prevalence of CVD in patients with OA, which significantly exceeds that in the general population [9–11]. An important link in the pathogenesis of OA is microcirculation disorders with activation and proliferation of endothelium and smooth muscle cells, vasospasm, aggregation of formed elements, stasis, deformation and reduction of the capillary network [1, 2, 15-20].

Endothelial dysfunction and hemorheological disorders characteristic of OA are considered as early predictors of atherosclerosis. The general pathogenetic mechanisms of these diseases suggest a high probability of atherosclerotic vascular lesions in patients with OA [3-6, 21].

It is known that along with a generalized lesion of small-caliber vessels, which is determined already at the early stages of the disease, changes in medium-sized vessels are also observed in OA [2, 5-12]. Peripheral arterial lesions according to angiography and ultrasound scanning of blood vessels in patients with OA were found with a significantly higher frequency when compared with the control group and was associated with a severe clinical course of the disease [11]. A number of studies in the study of medium-sized vessels in patients with OA demonstrated a predominant lesion of the ulnar arteries, which is a predictor of the development of digital necrosis [12-13]. A biopsy of the ulnar arteries revealed a narrowing of the lumen of the arteries, while there were no atherosclerotic plaques [8]. Angiography revealed stiff peripheral arteries in patients with OA [8]. Other researchers determined a decrease in the elasticity of the carotid arteries in patients with limited and, to a greater extent, diffuse form of OA [16]. According to the Scottish group for the study of systemic sclerosis (M.Ho, D.Veale, C.Eastmond), stenosis of the carotid arteries was observed in 64% of patients with OA at an average age of 57 (31-82) years and almost twice as often (35%) in control group. The frequency of atherosclerotic plaques and peripheral vascular disease was also higher among patients with OA, despite the absence of significant differences in the frequency of cardiovascular risk factors between the two groups [7, 14].

Thickening of the aortic walls, which is an independent factor of cardiovascular risk, was diagnosed in patients with OA, regardless of the severity of skin and kidney fibrosis, and also significantly differed from the control group [15].

Interest data is that the decrease in the reserve of coronary arteries according to the results of doppler echocardiography with contrast in patients with OA was determined with a higher frequency when compared with the control group [16].

A recent study showed a significant decrease in endothelium-dependent vasodilation as an early marker of atherosclerosis with a trend towards an increase in the thickness of the intima-media complex in patients with OA compared with the control group, while the groups did not differ in cardiovascular risk factors [17].

Along with the data of instrumental examination, confirming the diagnosis of atherosclerosis, clinical signs of atherosclerosis against the background of OA are also described. According to the results of the Edinburgh epidemiological study, the diagnosis of intermittent claudication was established in 22%, coronary heart disease (CHD) in 15%, cerebrovascular disease in 6.5% of patients with OA [9].

According to various studies, patients with OA are characterized by a high risk of mortality from cardiovascular diseases [18,19]. In a cause-of-death analysis of 344 patients with OA in Denmark, it was shown that the group of patients with death caused by other, non-OA conditions was twice as high as the group of patients whose direct cause of death was OA. At the same time, the main cause of death in the former was cardiovascular pathology [20].

Thus, the diagnosis of OA suggests the early development of vascular atherosclerosis, which is one of the main causes of death in patients. Research on the prevalence of atherosclerosis in patients with OA is

currently scarce, especially compared to the large number of studies on atherosclerosis in osteoarthritis (OA), rheumatoid arthritis (RA), and antiphospholipid syndrome (APS). The problem of the relationship between atherosclerosis and vascular damage in OA remains not fully understood.

The aim of this study was to estimation the frequency of traditional cardiovascular risk factors and clinical manifestations of atherosclerosis in patients with OA.

Material and methods

From 2023 to 2024, we examined 70 patients with a reliable diagnosis of OA (66 women and 4 men) admitted to the rheumatology, cardiorheumatology and rheumatology departments of the 1st clinic of the Tashkent Medical Academy. The average age of patients was 46 ± 10.8 years (from 20 to 64 years). The duration of the disease ranged from 6 months to 38 years, with an average of 10 (4-15) years. The criteria for inclusion in the study were a reliable diagnosis of OA (ARA criteria) [20] and the age of patients from 17 to 65 years.

The control group consisted of 50 "conditionally" healthy volunteers (employees of the department of the Tashkent Medical Academy) who do not have systemic rheumatic diseases, matched by sex (45 women and 5 men) and age (44.1 ± 7.4 years).

The study did not include patients and volunteers with clinical signs of infection, end-stage renal or hepatic insufficiency, uncontrolled diabetes mellitus.

To verify the diagnosis of OA and characteristics of organ pathology, all patients underwent instrumental studies, including chest X-ray, ECG, Echo-KG, Holter ECG monitoring (HM-ECG), functional pulmonary tests (spirometry, study of the diffusion capacity of the lungs).

In all patients of the main and control groups, classical risk factors for atherosclerosis were analyzed: a family history of cardiovascular diseases (CVD) in the next of kin (myocardial infarction (MI) or sudden death in men under 55 years of age, in women under 65 years of age) [21], an increase in body mass index (BMI) (weight, kg/height, $m^2 \geq 25$ kg/m²) [22], dyslipidemia (abnormal levels of one or more classes of lipoproteins [total cholesterol (CH) levels > 5.0 mmol/l, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL cholesterol) < 1.0 mmol/l, triglycerides (TG) > 1.7 mmol/l], arterial hypertension (systolic blood pressure (SBP) ≥ 140 mm Hg, diastolic (DBP) ≥ 90 mm Hg or taking antihypertensive drugs), smoking, menopause, diabetes mellitus. Total coronary risk (TCR%) (10-year risk of cardiovascular events) was assessed using the Framingham scale.

To identify clinical forms of atherosclerosis in patients with OA (n=60) and in the control group (n=45), an ultrasound scan of the carotid arteries was performed using a linear sensor with a radiation frequency of 7.5 MHz on a Voluson 730 Expert device (Austria) with measurement of the thickness of the intima complex - media (TIM) at three points (1 point - common carotid artery - 10 mm to the bulb; 2 point - 5-10 mm cranial from the beginning of the bulb; 3 point - internal carotid artery - 10 mm after bifurcation from two sides) and calculations average and maximum values of TIM. The presence of atherosclerosis was assessed by thickening of the intima-media complex (IMT from 0.9 to 1.2 mm) and the presence of atherosclerotic plaques (ATP) (local increase in IMT > 1.2 mm).

Statistical processing of the results was carried out using the Statistica 6.0 software package (StatSoft, USA). Quantitative values are given as $M \pm SD$ with correct distribution and as Me(LQ-UQ)-median with an interquartile range (25th - 75th percentile) with incorrect distribution of features. For the statistical evaluation of the results, nonparametric methods were used: the Mann-Whitney test, the calculation of Fisher's exact test, and Spearman's correlation analysis. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Comparison of traditional cardiovascular risk factors in patients with OA and in the control group did not reveal significant differences, except that the frequency of smoking was significantly higher in the control group ($p=0.002$), and menopause was more common among patients with OA ($p=0.005$) (Table. 2).

TFR% in patients with OA was 3(1-27) %, which coincided with the average value of TFR% in the control group - 3(1-15)%.

Table 2. Traditional cardiovascular risk factors in patients with OA

Risk factors for atherosclerosis:	Patients with OA n=70 n(%)	Control group n=50 n(%)
Heredity according to CVD	22 (31%)	18 (36%)
BMI $\geq$ 25 kg/m ²	28 (40%)	22 (44%)
Dyslipidemia	53 (76%)	34 (72%)
Arterial hypertension	25 (36%)	12 (24%)
Smoking	5 (7%)	14 (28%)
Menopause	38 (57%)	11 (24%)
Diabetes	3(4,3%)	-

* $p<0,05$

When analyzing the clinical manifestations of atherosclerosis, it turned out that coronary artery disease was determined more frequently among patients with OA. IHD was diagnosed in 9 (13%) patients with OA and only in 1 (2%) volunteer from the control group ($p<0.05$). MI (one case) was recorded only in the group of patients with OA, stroke - in one patient with OA and in 1 volunteer from the control group.

Comparison of blood lipid concentrations showed that the level of triglycerides in patients with OA was significantly higher than in the control group ($p<0.001$) (Table 3).

Table 3. Mean lipid values in OA patients and in the control group

Lipids: (mmol/l)	Patients with OA D, n=70	Control group, n=50
Cholesterol	5,5 (4,8-6,4)	5,6 (5,0-7,3)
Triglycerides	0,87 (0,63-1,76)*	0,55 (0,30-0,93)*
HDL	1,24 (0,99-1,68)	1,4 (1,21-1,62)

Me(LQ-UQ); * $p<0,001$

The mean and maximum IMT values of the carotid arteries, obtained by ultrasound scanning of these vessels, did not differ significantly in the groups of OA patients and controls. There was only a slight tendency to increase TIM max. (1.0 ± 0.36 and 0.88 ± 0.14) and the frequency of IMT thickening (42% and 38%, respectively) in patients with OA compared with the control group. Atherosclerotic plaques (IMT $>$ 1.2 mm) were determined in 10% of patients with OA and were absent in the control group ($p<0.05$) (Table 4).

Table 4. The thickness of the intima-media complex of the carotid arteries in patients with OA and in the control group

TIM, mm	Patients with OA n=60	Control group, n=45
TIM average	0,78 $\pm$ 0,18	0,74 $\pm$ 0,08
TIM middle right	0,77 $\pm$ 0,18	0,74 $\pm$ 0,09
TI M middle left	0,8 $\pm$ 0,2	0,75 $\pm$ 0,09
TIM maximum	1,0 $\pm$ 0,36	0,88 $\pm$ 0,14

TIM 0.9-1.2 (n,%)	25 (42%)	17 (38%)
TIM>1.2 (n,%)	6 (10%)*	0*

M±SD, n (%), *p<0.05

A high positive correlation was established between IMT average and IMT max. with the age of patients with OA (respectively, $r=0.64$, $t=6.28$, $p<0.001$ and $r=0.44$, $t=3.74$, $p<0.001$). Mean IMT also correlated with disease duration ($r=0.28$, $t=2.23$, $p<0.05$).

In the group of patients with OA, positive correlations were found between TFR% and IMT, both mean ($r=0.51$, $t=4.5$, $p=0.00003$) and max. ($r=0.41$, $t=3.4$, $p=0.001$). In addition, they revealed a correlation between mean IMT and cholesterol levels ($r=0.31$, $t=2.44$, $p<0.05$).

Conclusion

A high prevalence of cardiovascular pathology and atherosclerotic vascular lesions in patients with OA in the absence of significant differences in the frequency of major cardiovascular risk factors was also observed in other studies [7, 11-12, 14-17]. It can be assumed that the factors involved in the pathogenesis of this disease are of paramount importance in the development of early atherosclerosis in patients with OA. This assumption is confirmed by a series of studies that show that anti-endothelial antibodies, dysfunction of the coagulation and fibrinolytic systems, an increase in the level of homocysteine, CRP, and intercellular adhesion molecules significantly increase the risk of atherosclerosis in OA. Thus, in patients with OA, along with scleroderma angiopathy, there are clinical and subclinical signs of atherosclerosis. These data indicate the advisability of prescribing drugs that have a protective effect on the vascular wall - statins and antioxidants - to patients with OA.

References

1. Amaya-Amaya J, Sarmiento-Monroy JC, Caro-Moreno J, et al. Cardiovascular disease in latin american patients with osteoarthritis: a cross-sectional study and a systematic review. *Autoimmune Dis*. 2013;2013: Article ID 794383, 20 p. doi: 10.1155/2013/794383
2. Björnadal L, Yin L, Granath F, et al. Cardiovascular disease a hazard despite improved prognosis in patients with osteoarthritis: results from a Swedish population based study 1964-95. *J Rheumatol*. 2004;31(4):713-9.
3. Bruce IN. 'Not only... but also': factors that contribute to accelerated atherosclerosis and premature coronary heart disease in osteoarthritis. *Rheumatology (Oxford)*. 2005;44(12):1492-502. doi:10.1093/rheumatology/kei142
4. D'Cruz DP, Khamashta MA, Hughes GR. Osteoarthritis. *Lancet*. 2007;369(9561):587-96. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(07)60279-7
5. Doria A, Iaccarino L, Ghirardello A, et al. Long-term prognosis and causes of death in osteoarthritis. *Amer J Med*. 2006;119(8):700-6. doi: 10.1016/j.amjmed.2005.11.034
6. Esdaile JM, Abrahamowicz M, Grodzicky T, et al. Traditional Framingham risk factors fail to fully account for accelerated atherosclerosis in osteoarthritis. *Arthritis Rheum*. 2001;44(10):2331-7. doi: 10.1002/1529-0131(200110)44:103.0.CO;2-I
7. Fangtham M, Petri M. 2013 update: Hopkins lupus cohort. *Curr Rheumatol Rep*. 2013;15(9):360. doi:10.1007/s11926-013-0360-0
8. Ilyina AE, Klyukvina NG, Alexandrova EN et al. Atherosclerotic vascular lesions in osteoarthritis and antiphospholipid syndrome in men. *Clinical medicine*. 2006;(4):23-8 [Ilyina AE, Klyukvina NG,

- Aleksandrova EN, et al. Atherosclerotic vascular lesions in osteoarthritis and antiphospholipid syndrome in men. *Clinical Meditsina*. 2006;(4):23-8 (In Russ.)].
9. Kiani AN, Magder LS, Petri M. Mycophenolate mofetil (MMF) does not slow the progression of subclinical atherosclerosis in OA over 2 years. *Rheumatol Int*. 2012;32(9):2701-5. doi:10.1007/s00296-011-2048-y
 10. Liu Z, Davidson A. Taming lupus – a new understanding of pathogenesis is leading to clinical advances. *nature medicine*. 2012;18(6):871-82. doi: 10.1038/nm.2752
 11. Loeffen R, Spronk HM, ten Cate H. The impact of blood coagulability on atherosclerosis and cardiovascular disease. *J Thromb Haemost*. 2012;10(7):1207-16. doi: 10.1111/j.1538-7836.2012.04782.x 33. Boles J, Mackman N. Role of tissue factor in thrombosis in antiphospholipid antibody syndrome. *Lupus*. 2010;19(4):370-8. doi:10.1177/0961203309360810
 12. Magder LS, Petri M. Incidence of and risk factors for adverse cardiovascular events among patients with osteoarthritis. *Am J Epidemiol*. 2012;176(8):708-19. doi:10.1093/aje/kws130
 13. Manzi S, Meilahn EN, Rairie JE, et al. Age-specific incidence rates of myocardial infarction and angina in women with osteoarthritis: comparison with the Framingham study. *Amer J Epidemiol*. 1997;145(5):408-15. doi:10.1093/oxfordjournals.aje.a009122
 14. McMahan M, Grossman J, Chen W, et al. Inflammation and the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis in osteoarthritis. *Lupus*. 2006;15:59-69. doi: 10.1177/0961203306071668
 15. Motoki Y, Nojima J, Yanagihara M, et al. Anti-phospholipid antibodies contribute to arteriosclerosis in patients with osteoarthritis through induction of tissue factor expression and cytokine production from peripheral blood mononuclear cells. *Thromb Res*. 2012;130(4):667-73. doi:10.1016/j.thromres.2011.11.048
 16. Nossent J, Cikes N, Kiss E, et al. Current causes of death in osteoarthritis in Europe, 2000-2004: relation to disease activity and damage accrual. *Lupus*. 2007;16(5):309-17. doi:10.1177/0961203307077987
 17. Petri M. The lupus anticoagulant is a risk factor for myocardial infarction (but not atherosclerosis): Hopkins Lupus Cohort. *Thromb Res*. 2004;114(5-6):593-5. doi:10.1016/j.thromres.2004.07.012
 18. Rubin LA, Urowitz MB, Gladman DD. Mortality in osteoarthritis: the bimodal pattern revisited. *Q J Med*. 1985;55(216):87-98.
 19. Sinicato NA, da Silva Cardoso PA, Appenzeller S. Risk factors in cardiovascular disease in osteoarthritis. *Curr Cardiol Rev*. 2013;19(1):15-9.
 20. Trager J, Ward MM. Mortality and causes of death in osteoarthritis. *Curr Opin Rheumatol*. 2001;13:345-51. doi: 10.1097/00002281-200109000-00002
 21. Urowitz MB, Bookman AA, Koehler BE, et al. The bimodal mortality pattern of osteoarthritis. *Am J Med*. 1976;60(2):221-5. doi: 10.1016/0002-9343(76)90431-9
 22. Van Leuven SI, van Wijk DF, Volger OL, et al. Mycophenolate mofetil attenuates plaque inflammation in patients with symptomatic carotid artery stenosis. *atherosclerosis*. 2010;211(1):231-6. doi: 10.1016/j.atherosclerosis.2010.01.043